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Follow-up episode psilocybin.

Autors:

Yvonne Höller, Professor at the University of Akureyri, Akureyri, Iceland (yvonne@unak.is) – text in black font.

Jón Ingi Hlynsson, Master student at the University of Iceland, Reykjavík, Iceland (jih10@hi.is) – text in red font.

Hi, this is Yvonne Höller from the Faculty of Psychology at the University of Akureyri and this is your Cognitive Neuroscience podcast. Today we are following up on one of your favourite topics: Psilocybin - and we have a special guest!

Hi Jón Ingi, how are you?

I am doing good! Pleased to be here! How are you?

I am fine and I am so glad to meet you here, thank you so much for joining us! We know each other from our collaboration in the EpiC SAD study, and we will learn more about this epic study in one of the upcoming episodes, but now, would you like to let our audience know who you are?

Thanks for having me! Yes, indeed, we have been collaborating on the EPIC-SAD study which has been quite rewarding!

But to your question, I am a clinical graduate student at the University of Iceland – I am currently engaged in quite a few research projects at varying capacities, the EPIC-SAD study being one of them although my involvement in that particular project is somewhat limited to administering the MINI diagnostic interview.

And we are so thankful you have been doing this and are still doing it! But we will hear more about that in an upcoming episode. So, what about your research so far?

Most of my research so far has been psychometric, although I did also investigate the effects of the war-outbreak in Ukraine on psychopathological symptoms in a Swedish treatment-seeking sample. But my most recent publication revolves around mapping out the potential negative effects of psychedelic-assisted therapy, specifically, psychotherapy that is delivered while patients are under the influence of psilocybin – the psychoactive compound in so-called "magic mushrooms".

And that is why we need you here today. We had a podcast with some basics about psilocybin when it got really popular, but since then, some things have changed. Would you like to tell us how you got into doing research about psilocybin and what you find fascinating about this substance?

Right, and I listened to that episode in preparation for today and you'd be surprised how many things change, but still remain the same!

But so, I got into this research somewhat by happenstance... As you know, the potential benefits of psychedelic-assisted therapy have been a popular discussion point for quite some time now. I was invited to join a research group that had begun evaluating the potential drawbacks and negative impacts of psilocybin in psychotherapy. What intrigued me

the most was the chance to map out psilocybin's negative effects and identify potential drawbacks of psychedelic-assisted therapy. However, much credit is due to my co-authors, especially Moa Nordin, who conducted the interviews and conceptualized the study, but also to Per Carlbring and Jakob Håkansson without whom the project would not have materialized.

That was in Stockholm, right?

That's right!

I should say: The famous University of Stockholm!

In our last podcast about psilocybin, we criticized that there were no good clinical trials that control the placebo effect efficiently about psilocybin. We were specifically complaining about this great Lancet publication that was conducted in 12 patients, only, and it was open label. So, you as the expert have a good overview, what about the quality of evidence - Has that changed by now?

Right! You actually brought up many of the same issues two years ago in your podcast as I have with the evidence, or perhaps lack of evidence, but let me provide a short overview of how the field looks from my perspective at the moment.

So open-label studies are indeed a very prominent problem in the field of psychedelic sciences – open-label essentially means that there is no control group. I have a funny – or not-so-funny – anecdote from an open-label study that I think is appropriate for me to tell you about. A fairly recent open-label study – with 27 participants – provided two doses of psilocybin accompanied by supportive therapy to people with major depression. They followed up on these people a year later and found that 60% of the participants were no longer depressed. This seems like a huge effect... but wait, there are some major caveats to this... as you alluded to, there was no control group... but worse yet, we know that depression is episodic. And we also know that the expected 12-month recovery rate for depression is above 50% -- so given that, this 60% of people that no longer meet diagnostic criteria for depression does not seem so impressive anymore.

Oh, stop stop stop... so the authors sold this result as a great impact on depression, but actually, it might be just natural remission?

Natural remission is at least a very probable alternative explanation for these findings. Now, I am not saying that the authors had any intention of malice in mind... but this is just an exemplar for the many things that are plaguing the field of psychedelic sciences. We have these open-label trials, but other pertinent problems include small sample sizes, moving the goalposts in terms of outcomes reported versus registered (meaning that if you look at the clinicaltrials.gov registry and see the edits that are all too often made after data has been collected, it looks like primary outcomes are sometimes bumped down to secondary outcomes and vice versa – and this is essentially a problem with researcher's degrees of freedom), then we have the issue of conflicts of interest which are not always properly disclosed, and the list goes on and on.

Like, we don't even really know what the mechanism of action is in these psychedelic-assisted therapy studies – some have attributed it to neural entropy, while others suggest that the suggestive experience of the trip itself is the key component.

Ok stop here. Neural entropy? What do you mean? I have done research on entropy measures in the EEG, but I suppose you mean something else.

It might actually be the same thing. Entropy is a measure of the disorder or randomness within a system. Neural entropy draws from the entropic brain hypothesis which states that during a psychedelic experience, there is an increase in the connectivity between different brain networks that are normally not very strongly connected.

The concept of the **entropic brain**¹ suggests that when under the influence of psychedelics, our brain enters a state of increased disorder or entropy, which is quite different from our normal waking consciousness. Studies using neuroimaging have found that measures of entropy in the brain did indeed increase during the acute effects of psychedelics, thus supporting this idea. The increased entropic brain states observed under psychedelics can help explain the synesthetic experiences that are commonly reported, such as sounds inducing specific colors and touch evoking specific sounds.

Please tell me about your understanding of entropy from an EEG perspective.

Haha, I can tell you that now I would like to do EEG on people taking psychedelics to see what is really happening there.

Well yes of course, the EEG is my hometown in cognitive neuroscience. Entropy is, in other words, the information content. The more complex, the more information there is. When you have a list of numbers that is just 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 ... you can easily predict what the next number will be – it will be 0 and then a 1 and then again, a 0... the information content in this list is very small. If we stick to the 0s and 1s the information content is a lot higher for a sequence like this: 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 So, I tried to make a pretty random list of 0s and 1s here with which it is not possible to predict the next number. You need the whole sequence to get the information, not just a few numbers based on which you can predict how this would go on. This is basically entropy in the electroencephalogram. We measure brain signals and since we digitize them, they are just numbers. And these numbers can be quite a regular pattern, with low entropy, or a quite irregular, or complex pattern, so to speak with high entropy.

Combining entropy with the concept of connectivity is a little bit different but still the same. In research using magnetic resonance imaging the brain entropy is measured as the many different states a brain can be in. In the EEG when we measure connectivity, we cannot really say there is a connection between one and the other part because we are only looking at these signals. But if two signals from two different sites of the brain look very similar, we infer they might be connected as they exchange information and do a similar thing. So, if connectivity is increased between areas that normally do not the same thing, we add new states of brain activity. For example, you mentioned synesthesia, that is a number has a specific color etc. That sounds very much like we should be able to explain it with connectivity between the brain area storing the number and the brain area storing the color. Normally they should not be connected but in some people they are.

OK so the idea is that these brain changes solve the problem of depression. That sounds also plausible to me as in depression the brain is rather inactive, slower than usual, if we look at the EEG. That makes the effect of psychedelics pretty credible.

But we are forgetting one thing; these substances are being administered in the context of therapy! And there have not been any systematic evaluations that disaggregate the effects of therapy from the psychedelic substance effects properly, or at least to the best of my knowledge there have not been any proper studies that effectively evaluate this problem.

¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0149763422002822>

Even in our study, some therapists claimed that music perpetuates invasive negative self-experiences during the psychedelic-assisted therapy session. Music therapy is a type of therapy, but funnily enough, music is routinely used in psychedelic-assisted therapy – so the question remains: What effects are explained by the music and what effects are explained by the therapy and what effects are explained by the psychedelics. So far, we just don't really know.

Yes, and for music it is like for many other alternative therapies such as poetry therapy and so on: The effect sizes are not such that you can just listen to music or write a poem if you are depressed, and you will be fine. Although it definitely helps to engage in activities like writing or listening to music, you cannot cure your mental health problem with that alone.

No that's absolutely right! But my main qualm with all of this is the lack of disaggregation of what has what effect.

A recent paper published late last year, by Michiel van Elk and Eiko Fried titled "History repeating: guidelines to address common problems in psychedelic science" provides a great overview of the most pertinent problems that are diluting the literature². In that paper, which is very accessible by the way, both for people used to scientific discourse and people who are perhaps dabbling in science and trying to understand and disseminate research findings like journalists, but in that paper, van Elk and Eiko Fried provide a comprehensive overview of the problems that currently plague psychedelic science – but what's maybe more impressive is that they also provide potential solutions to these problems and present readers with a set a criteria that can be used to better understand the quality of evidence presented in each research paper on this topic.

But to summarize our discussion on the quality of the evidence, as of now it just simply is not good enough to draw any major conclusions from it by my estimation... and the quality of evidence definitely does not align with the media hype surrounding these substances!

OK so to conclude: The situation is not much different now as compared to about 2 years ago when I did the first episode on psilocybin. But now let's look at your study which found some important additional information on the treatment with psilocybin– you did not conduct a randomized clinical trial but chose a different approach. What did you do?

That's right! The situation has not changed a whole lot, although we do have more studies, many of them have questionable designs... and another thing that's quite distressing, and I think you also made this point in your previous episode on the topic, the majority of the trials... or at least a WHOLE lot of them are being conducted by the same team...

But to our study: We did not conduct a randomized controlled trial, but instead our study was qualitative. So let me break that down a little bit. What we did was that we recruited therapists and mental health professionals who are currently providing or have provided therapy to patients who are under the influence of psilocybin. So... after recruiting them, we interviewed them and transcribed the interviews verbatim. Then we employed a thematic analysis, which essentially boils down to evaluating the transcripts and looking for themes in the responses that the participants gave us. We evaluated both short-term negative effects and long-term negative effects through this method and 7 themes emerged in total, 3 short-term negative effects themes and 4 long-term negative effects themes.

That is interesting! Of course, now we want to know: What are these short-term and long-term negative effects!

² <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/20451253231198466>

In terms of short-term negative effects, we found short-term **negative reactions** to psilocybin dosing sessions, including physical, cognitive, and emotional negative reactions. We also found **undesirable changes in the therapy relationship**, such as *risky power dynamics*, and **challenging self-experiences** where patients found the dosing frightening, invasive, and overwhelming.

That sounds bad enough – but can you explain to our listeners what are risky power dynamics?

Sure! Risky power dynamics refer to the increased chance of clients being taken advantage of during psilocybin dosing. The drug can lead to a quick bond between therapist and client, similar to a parent-child relationship. This can lead to unequal power in the relationship and the therapist's needs being prioritized over the client's well-being. Clients can also be easily influenced in this state, which adds to the risk. In our study, therapists described this vulnerability and imbalance as "extreme", and this suggestibility is far more problematic than in conventional therapy. This is the case even for therapists who are used to handling difficult situations...

Maybe you say something here?

However, the long-term negative effects were more distressing in my opinion. For example, we found increased long-term **destabilization**... this meant that patient defense or avoidance mechanisms became disrupted, leading to decreased coping abilities.

That sounds like something you totally don't want to happen. But as not all of our listeners are psychotherapists and know these terms, could you explain what happens for example if defense or avoidance mechanisms are disrupted and what are coping abilities?

It sounds pretty bad, right? And you're right, you don't want that to happen!

You can basically think of all these terms as the same thing. They all approximate the same underlying concept of "if I am scared and do something, then I will survive". Its a way to cope.

So let me give an example of an avoidance mechanism that can become disrupted. Imagine that you're an ancient caveman who one day has an encounter with a lion. And on that particular day, you happen to have a stone in your pocket... You've been told by the leader of your tribe that this stone has magical properties, that it can hide your smell if you encounter a dangerous animal. So anyway, you encounter this lion and get scared, right? As you should be. And you hide in a bush that's next to your trail... Some time passes by, and the lion goes away, and you run like mad back to your cave. Thank God you had the stone right?

Not right. Because us "logical" 21st-century humans realize that there are no stones that hide your smell from a lion. But if you believe that the stone has these properties, and it appeared to work – I mean, the lion didn't eat you right? – then you probably won't ever leave your cave without the stone again. Understandably, right? You think it saves your life.

Okay, so let's put this in context. In this example, you attribute that fact that you're still alive and remain uneaten by lions to live another day to the fact that you were carrying the stone. But again, assuming that this is just a regular old stone, the stone itself has nothing to do with the fact that you're alive! These are what we call avoidance behaviors or safety behaviors – or even defense mechanisms if you are so inclined ... the difference being the school of thought you subscribe to. And one of the things we want to help people realize in

therapy is that they don't need to preform these avoidant safety behaviors to survive their day.

Let me give another, less abstract, example. Imagine a person who has a fear of blushing. One of the things this person might do to survive their day is to put on specific makeup to hide potential instances of blushing. However, the problem with that is that then you start to cope with your day by putting on this makeup... you just can't have your day and you certainly can't socially interact without this makeup. And if you have a fear of blushing, and believe that the makeup is responsible for your ability to interact socially, then it makes total sense that you put it on! It's a logical but dysfunctional behavior!

So the problem we found was that people had perhaps made some therapeutic gains, dropped some of their avoidant safety behaviors, but then following a psilocybin session, these unhelpful behaviors come back. So for instance, some treatment receivers start to suppress their emotions or avoid certain experiences to a greater degree than before receiving the psilocybin treatment.

Another issue we found was that some people dropped all of their avoidant safety behaviors at once following the psilocybin experience, and remember this type of therapy is usually short! The reason for why this is a problem is that we humans need some mechanisms to help us through the day. We need to be able to function... like I said, these types of behaviors are logically dysfunctional. But removing them completely all at once is no small change, and doing so without providing the people receiving this therapy with tools to develop more helpful alternatives can make the client more vulnerable to various risks, especially if their environments outside the therapy room is not fostering and welcoming.

Maybe you say something here?

Now another interesting long-term effect we found was **difficulties adjusting to life after treatment**, with the insights gained during therapy overwhelming the people receiving therapy to such an extent that their coping abilities were further diminished.

We also found long-term **complications in the treatment relationship** – clients desiring continued contact after treatment ends, and this was often due to dependency, idealization, and idolization, but also because of romantic transference and blurred professional boundaries. We got reports of therapists saying that they found it could be hard to resist romantic feelings, as the strong emotions in the session make it hard to turn down romantic advances.

Oh wait, does that mean the clients fell in love with their therapist?

Exactly! But more of a dependency

Sounds like a bad Hollywood movie. I think we have to explain to our audience also why sometimes we say patients, and sometimes we say clients.

Yeah, I guess that's my bad, haha! I do prefer the term client, and that conveys more respect than the term patient. So, I do tend to use that, but it is not always obvious what metaphorical client I am referring to, so I sometimes use patient in English. (more commonly used, so maybe it's an *appeal to the masses fallacy* in by spoken language)

But let me tell you about the final long-term effect we found... which were **undesirable outcomes** in the long-term. Now this included a worsening of the original condition that people seeking therapy experienced or even the development of new symptoms.

This all sounds like I would rather not want to take psilocybin if I had depression. Can you say for sure that these are problems that arose because these patients took psilocybin, or is it possible that they would have happened anyhow?

I cannot say for sure, no. These problems might have happened anyhow, but it is definitely interesting that these themes emerged ... and what's perhaps even more interesting is the fact that people under the influence of psilocybin are highly suggestable and at an increased risk of being taken advantage of... and therefore I believe we must be extra vigilant when doing these kinds of research and especially therapists who need to be aware of the heightened power imbalance – which is already unequal but even more when their clients are under the influence of psilocybin.

I understand this is because of the study design. What advantage does it have to collect data that way as compared to randomized clinical trials?

That's a good question! So basically, when one aspires to conduct a randomized controlled trial, the definition of variables must be clear at the onset. There had not been any proper evaluations of the potential negative effects of psilocybin in the context of therapy so defining the variables would have been next to impossible – we wanted to explore whether there were any commonalities between the perceived negative effects of this kind of therapy, and to do so, we used a qualitative study design. Now, one of the implications of this study is that it can serve as a bedrock for generating a questionnaire to evaluate these themes at a larger scale.

Right, we should check how many patients fall in love with their therapist if they take psilocybin or not in a randomized controlled trial.

Exactly! Now I must note a key limitation of this design in general and a limitation of our study specifically.

We are all ears...

When you set out to detect themes in participant responses, you do run the risk of implicitly biasing the results to force out themes. We were very much aware of this, and much credit is due for Moa Nordin whom both conducted the interviews and led their analysis under excellent supervision. We were also lucky to have a very talented qualitative researcher onboard, Jakob Hakansson, and Per Carlbring whom has, among other things, been involved with studies evaluating negative effects of psychological treatment in general. All in all, we took every conceivable measure to safeguard against biasing the themes implicitly, and as is probably evident in the paper, we made sure to include lots of actual quotes from the participants to hammer home the themes.

With regards to the limitation specific to our study, it should be noted that we only interviewed treatment providers. It is absolutely conceivable that different themes would emerge if we had interviewed the patients that received the treatment. But then again, doing so would come with its own set of limitations.

Let me tell you an interesting story that relates to this.

I saw an interview recently with a woman in Kastljós³ (an Icelandic news segment) that had received psilocybin from someone claiming to be a therapist (meðferðaraðili in Icelandic) –

³ <https://www.ruv.is/frettir/menning-og-daegurmal/2024-03-16-eg-er-alltaf-hraedd-um-ad-eg-se-i-raun-og-veru-ad-missa-vitid-407409?fbclid=IwAR2v->

and I say someone because I don't know the details of this case personally, but only saw the news segment and therefore am not in a position to evaluate the professional merits of the person that delivered the supposed treatment – but anyway, this woman had seen a Netflix documentary "How to Change Your Mind" about the potential benefits of psilocybin and decided to have a go at it. She reaches out to this treatment provider and following the psilocybin trip, her experiences align with many of the same experiences that the treatment providers reported in our study. And while I do realize that anecdotal evidence does not amount to much, it is certainly interesting – to say the least – to note the parallels between our study from the perspective of treatment providers and this woman's subjective experience of this kind of treatment.

Right, we can recommend our Icelandic listeners to not just go to someone who claims to be a therapist and administrate psilocybin. I have heard from a dear colleague who is an expert but does not want to be associated in any way with this drug that he is very concerned about the way things are done in Iceland, since people show up in the emergency department of the Psychiatric hospital because they had a trip and suffer from the consequences, but their treatment provider would not deal with it, or possibly, could not even help. So, there is a big danger in just giving it a go.

Yes! Please be careful!

But in research, however way you slice it, when studying psilocybin, you are bound by a central constraint, and that relates to the sampling process. Whether you interview treatment providers or treatment recipients, you can only talk to people that are already positively oriented towards psilocybin. One thing Michiel van Elk and Eiko Fried suggest as a potential solution to some of these problems is to recruit psychedelic-naïve participants – they would assumably both be easier to fool... and I mean that technically, as when conducting proper clinical trials, it is essential to preserve the blindness of participants to their allocated treatment condition – but they also don't necessarily have as strong of an a-priori positive bend towards these substances. Just imagine, do you think it's easy to get people to participate in psilocybin trials if they have a negative prior experience of those substances? I don't think so, and thus the sampling procedure is going to be faulty if one of the criteria for participation – and it often is – is a priori experiences.

Oh yes, just people who want to try or have tried already Magic Mushrooms will take more Magic Mushrooms.

Right! But when interviewing treatment providers like we did in our study, it is somewhat self-evident that only those providers that have a positive view of psilocybin, to begin with, are going to be included in the sample... you can't ask people about their perceptions of the negative effects of psychedelic-assisted therapy if they have never actually delivered such therapy.

And again, you run into the same problem with treatment recipients, obviously, you can't ask people about an experience they've never had! So, there is an inherent sampling bias in these kinds of studies... people who participate are positively oriented towards psychedelics to begin with... and this is a limitation that is far too seldom considered by my estimation in the trials that have purported to find a positive effect of these kinds of treatments!

That is a valid point and indeed difficult to tackle. That means, we are not going to have good studies on the subject any soon. When reading the article, I found it so fascinating that

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there were some therapists in the sample that provided the psychedelic medication “illegally” – how can that even happen? Are patients not informed well about the procedure or are they accepting that they do something illegal, or are there not enough therapists around that provide the same procedure in a legal way?

HAH! Yeah, that is quite funny, right? I'd like to first caution against using the term medication. Medication carries a specific connotation, namely the term medication suggests that this is something that you can buy from your local pharmacist. That just simply is not the case in Iceland, although places like Australia have recognized psychedelics as a medication even though an expert opinion audited by them advised against it.

Oh yes, I will stick to say “magic mushrooms” from now on.

Now, having said that, psilocybin is available for purchase in cities like Amsterdam – but there it is not advertised as a medicinal substance, but rather a recreational drug. These substances have not been cleared through proper treatment trials ... yet ... and I realize that although I may have been giving the impression that I am fundamentally against their use, I don't think that they could not have their place. My point is simply that the data is not in yet, the studies that have been conducted so far are not very well designed – but that in itself is a whole different can of worms!

Hm yes. If I try to be optimistic on this, I could say that there might be some people who might benefit from it – I could think that it might work in the format of individualized therapies, that means that some people will benefit from it, and we just have to find out who these people are before giving them the substance. And I also summon the magic mushrooms could work if we know the dose-response relationship better, so how much does a 60kg heavy person need to get this kind of response, and how much do we have to give a 90kg person to get the same response, and how much of too much will provoke side effects.

So, get this... one of the consistent findings across the studies that have been conducted so far is that for the psychedelic substance to influence you, the so-called "trip" is key. And specifically, for the substance to exert a detectable influence, the person participating in a study must feel the trip come on – and the trip itself, the altered state of mind that these substances induce, is actually responsible for the effects that then get reported in studies. This had been alluded to in a study on personality changes, but there they found that people who were administered a psilocybin dose that induced a trip increased the personality trait Openness to Experience – which can roughly be thought of as the creativity dimension – and this effect was still detectable one year later⁴.

But more recently, some brilliant researchers conducted a blinded study⁵ where they administered either a placebo or a psychoactive substance – ketamine specifically – to individuals with depression who were in an induced sleep state using surgical anesthesia... so they could not know whether they had received the drug or the placebo. The interesting thing is that they found no differences in depressive symptom reductions between the placebo group and the drug administration group... and this supports the notion that the trip itself is essential. But this has a very annoying consequence... this means that we have no idea how to properly design blinded studies to evaluate these psychedelic substances, and that's a problem!

⁴ MacLean, K. A., Johnson, M. W., & Griffiths, R. R. (2011). Mystical Experiences Occasioned by the Hallucinogen Psilocybin Led to Increases in the Personality Domain of Openness. *Journal of Psychopharmacology (Oxford, England)*, 25(11), 1453–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881111420188>

⁵ Lij, T. R., Smith, A. E., Flohr, J. R., Okada, R. L., Nyongesa, C. A., Cianfichi, L. J., Hack, L. M., Schatzberg, A. F., & Heifets, B. D. (2023). Randomized trial of ketamine masked by surgical anesthesia in patients with depression. *Nature Mental Health*, 1(11), 876–886. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44220-023-00140-x>

Oh yes, we do not want to put all study participants in anesthesia to have them blinded so they cannot tell whether they had a trip or not.

Right, and that study does seem to support the notion that the trip, or the subjective experience is a key component!

But to your question about the illegal provision! So obviously these substances are illegal in Scandinavia and therefore a large portion of our sample either were currently or had at some point previously provided the treatment illegally.

So, the therapists had done illegal things in their treatment. Uff, that is quite a message.

This can easily happen, and documentaries like the one I mentioned earlier are driving up the demand for this, and the hype related to these novel treatments is not helping, at all!

However, some of the participants in our study did provide therapy legally, and this can be due to the treatment being provided in a research context or the like.

Of course, in research we can do such things, but we have to go through thorough bioethical evaluation and the participants in those studies will get monitored properly, and they even get an insurance that would pay if something would go horribly wrong. This is the way to do it with new possible treatment approaches.

Another somewhat unrelated issue is that I also found it interesting that the therapists had so many different backgrounds – which types of psychotherapy was psilocybin combined with?

It was a sort of free-for-all approach. We had therapists who had clinical training in cognitive behavioral therapy, acceptance and commitment therapy, psychodynamic therapy, and internal family systems therapy. And obviously this is a problem, but what's perhaps worse is that this "free-for-all" approach when it comes to type of therapy provided is the norm in psychedelics-assisted therapy studies.

So, get this... There are no guidelines on who can provide the treatment, even in Australia where it is recognized as a medicine – so for example, in a study on MDMA, the different types of therapy provided included a wide variety of different therapeutic approaches such as emotion-focused, psychodynamic, transpersonal, existential, or nondirective therapies, internal family systems, voice dialog, psychosynthesis, Hakomi, sensorimotor therapy, and holotropic breathwork.

Taken together, this exemplifies the lack of standardized training and requirements for therapists. There are currently no formal minimum requirements for professional psychiatrists or psychologists to apply psychedelic therapy.

And the study says they were based in Scandinavia – so they were not all in Sweden?

As you probably noticed in the paper, we selectively disclosed the sample characteristics in an effort to maintain confidentiality with our participants... and pretty much all I can say is that they were based in Scandinavia. Like we already discussed, the provision of this treatment is illegal in Scandinavia, barring research contexts, and therefore we don't want to compromise the identities of our participants by providing more information than is absolutely necessary for the results.

I totally understand, we are not going to tell on those brave therapists who were so nice to help out in your research project.

I still find the issue of all these different therapy types super interesting. I come from Austria where the Psychotherapy landscape is quite complicated – as far as I know, you need to choose a school, that can be cognitive behavioral therapy, psychoanalysis, humanistic therapy and so on – and then you spend maybe 10 years between the education itself and the supervised therapy and self-experience before you actually work as a therapist. In Iceland, this is quite different, would you like to tell our listeners the path how to become a clinical psychologist in Iceland, since you are currently on that path?

Right! So, in Iceland, you don't really choose a school per se, although one school of thought is definitely more prominent than the others – namely CBT.

Right, my impression was that this is the only thing existing in Iceland, and you become a therapist by taking this master's in clinical psychology, which – I would say – 90% of the Bachelor students I supervise aim for, and this is not a realistic plan for most of them as the programs have a limited number of students they take in every year. How was that for you, how did you decide to go for this highly competitive path?

Well, funnily enough, I didn't intend to become a clinical psychologist to begin with. I was – and obviously still am – fascinated by research and other aspects of psychology. But then a very poignant question was posed to my class in the last semester of my bachelor's program by Petur Tyrfinngsson: Why study psychology if not to alleviate human suffering and promote well-being... and to this question I have yet to find a good response.

So, I realize that research can help people at mass, but there is just something about the opportunity to get to see a person face-to-face in a bad place and guiding them towards a path of betterment that I find fulfilling. I had a long think about this, and truly I cannot conceive of anything more meaningful to do on a daily basis – like a 9-5 job – than being of service as a psychologist and therefore I sort of ended up in my current program. But this decision antagonized me for a long time before I eventually made it, as I did another master's degree more oriented towards research while thinking this though in Stockholm. And now I have sort of decided that I don't want to give up being a clinician, but I don't want to give up research either... so I just plan on doing both, haha!

Haha, I think I did it similarly but never got to the area of psychology I wanted to work in – which was not clinical psychology but marketing psychology. I got terribly stuck in research early on and I can tell you I love this job and do not limit it to 9 to 5, but that is a whole different story. How is this education for psychotherapists in Sweden, where the study was done?

In Sweden you do choose, and you choose early! I looked at the prospects of getting licensed in Sweden when I was living there actually, and it turns out you need to do a program called the psychologist program (psykologprogrammet in Swedish) and that is 300 ECTS, and essentially combines the bachelor's and master's in a single package. And thus, you need to pick that when starting university and there would have been a fair bit of checks and balances that would have been necessary for me to go through if I would have wanted to get my license there, but that would have started with an enrollment at the bachelor's level and then (maybe) get some courses accredited.

Now, another thing that's interesting about the psychologist program in Sweden is that you don't only need to choose that specific program, but you also need to choose a school of thought. And they offer either psychodynamic or cognitive behavioral training, and as far as I know, this is something you choose in the beginning. I could have that wrong, and maybe one can change midway through, but this was my understanding, and I'm sure my Swedish colleagues will educate me on this if I have gotten it wrong, haha.

Yes, the psychodynamic vs. cognitive behavior school is also quite a thing in Austria, actually at my home University I got the impression these two schools do not like each other very much, but that takes us too far from where we were at now. I conclude there is quite some difference in the education of people who may provide psychotherapy within and between countries. Now, back to the study, what can we conclude, or what take-home message would you give a person who asks you: Should I try psilocybin?

I try to refrain from giving advice, and the copout answer would obviously be to simply cite the law... it's illegal, hence don't do it. Now, I realize that's not the answer you're looking for, so let me say this: If a person comes to me to ask if they should try psilocybin, my immediate response would be "Why do you want to try psilocybin?" – and then take it from there. However, in a gun-to-my-head scenario, and I have to say yes or no, then I'm inclined to say no. And I can tell you why.

Like I said before, we found in our study these negative effects – both long-term and short-term negative effects... and the average person should interpret our findings as evidence of the importance of exercising caution:

Be cautious of unverified claims that psilocybin is a cure-all for psychological disorders. Psilocybin induces a potent altered state of mind, and it's not self-evident that consuming psychedelic mushrooms is beneficial for everyone. Our study suggests that potential negative effects of these substances, especially for vulnerable individuals seeking psychotherapy, are not yet fully understood. While existing research presents promising findings, we need to exercise caution before endorsing psilocybin as a viable treatment for mental disorders. The potential adverse effects of these treatments are still understudied.

Now, admittedly, negative effects of treatment also happen in garden-variety psychotherapy but when they happen in psychedelic-assisted therapy, there is an added risk factor. Let me give an example:

One surprising finding we found was that many treatment providers reported issues with romantic transference and blurred professional boundaries. Even for experienced therapists, managing romantic transference proved to be a challenge.

Yes, love is a complicated issue. What are the problems with that in a therapeutic setting?

It is a complicated issue, but we are talking about individuals that are abusing their situation though, so let's not confuse that with love – romantic transference is the technical terminology in psychodynamic schools of thought, but let's make this perfectly clear: Here we are talking about experienced therapists having problems with resisting the urge to "hit on" their clients...

Now, I don't know what to make of that, but we know that people with mental disorders are considered a vulnerable population... and there have been reports of sexual abuse in the past from therapists when their patients are in this altered state, which makes the already vulnerable individuals even more vulnerable!

Yes, I have heard about that for example in patients in an acute manic phase. I wonder how therapists cannot control themselves in such a situation, but let's stick to the topic. Did you find differences between the different types of psychotherapy?

That's a great question, but unfortunately, we didn't assess that specifically. One can assume that there are differences between someone that receives this treatment from a cold and task-oriented CBT therapist versus a relationship-oriented, more humanistic perhaps, psychodynamic therapist. But again, we didn't look into that specifically, and such

comparisons would probably be somewhat meaningless as we did not have a large sample size – for obvious reasons, as this is a qualitative study that takes an intense amount of time to conduct and analyze – and therefore if there had been any differences between types of psychotherapeutic orientation, I would not be confident that those differences would be representative of the differing schools of thought – the alternative explanation that people differ in their ability to form treatment alliances would be a major limitation of such analyses.

So, no food for the psychoanalyst versus CBT debate that was going on at my home-University. Anyhow, some of our audience sits in Iceland. Therefore, I have to ask whether you can tell me more about the stuff going on in Iceland regarding magic mushrooms?

Yes, I am. So, we already discussed the Kastljós segment, but aside from that there have been reports of people providing this kind of treatment – and if I remember correctly, at least one such case has ended up being discussed by the ethical committee of psychologists in Iceland. But sure, I have also heard anecdotal reports from people that are receiving psychedelic-assisted therapy in Iceland...

So again, or even more concrete: What is your opinion on psilocybin: Take it or leave it?

I'm sorry, but you won't catch me making a general statement about psilocybin, haha! And this is for various reasons, but first and foremost, I am not one to tell people what they should do.

I do, however, encourage people to make informed decisions.

Having said that, I can tell you that from my understanding of the evidence so far, in a therapeutic setting – I'd probably leave it for now...

I do, however, again, want to emphasize that I am not against psychedelics... I think it's very possible that they have their place in medicine, and maybe they even work as good or better than some established medications, but the evidence just isn't there yet.

And for recreational users who want to try this out, gain some insights and the like. I want to remind people of a quote from Carl Jung: Beware of unearned wisdom. And I think our results definitely support that notion.

Thank you so much Jón Ingi !

Thank you for having me! It has been a pleasure to discuss this with you!

(perhaps you could link to my blog for people interested in following my research:
www.jonhlynsson.com)